

the F₂ populations. The parameters evaluated were a) number of populations selected, b) phenotypic variability, and c) neck B1 score.

Good combining progenitors had the majority of the crosses selected, showed medium to high phenotypic variability, and had neck B1 scores not above 6 in

any cross. Araguaia, A8-204-1, Cuiabana, and IRAT216 were included in this group (see table). A second group with a lower combining ability included Cabacçu, CNA4640, CNA5180, and IAC82-276. CNA4157, Mut. Makouta 41-1-3, and TOM 1-3 showed poor combining ability.

A few single cross progenitors from the indica group were combined with japonicas, but the preliminary data did not show good results. The crosses produced very high phenotypic variability and susceptibility to neck B1. □

Breeding methods

Segregation of aroma character in F₂ hybrid rice grain

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F₂ seeds from five F₁ rice hybrids derived from aromatic CMS line Xiang xiang IIA and five restorer varieties were tasted to identify aroma.

Segregation was 15 nonaromatic: 1 aromatic grain (see table), indicating

Segregation of aroma in F₂ seeds borne by hybrids. HHRRC, Hunan, China.

Hybrid	Scented seed (no.)	Nonscented seed (no.)	χ^2	1 = 15	P
Xiang Xiang II A/PH137	67	933	0.27		>0.50
Xiang Xiang II A/26 Zhai Zao	59	941	0.15		>0.50
Xiang Xiang II A/Ming Tei 63	65	935	0.07		>0.75
Xiang Xiang II A/Ce 64	58	942	0.34		>0.50
Xiang Xiang II A/F 200	60	940	0.07		>0.75

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i \frac{k(UQ - EI - \frac{1}{2})^2}{E}$$

that aroma in the CMS line was controlled by 2 recessive genes. Absence of either gene resulted in nonaromatic grains.

The F₁ hybrids do not have an aroma during growth, but seed processing releases their aroma. □

Performance of two rice hybrids under upland conditions with and without fertilizer

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Experimental rice hybrids V41A/ IR54 and V41A/Sadang, developed for irrigated conditions in Indonesia, were compared with maintainer V20B, male parent Sadang, conventional upland varieties Tondano and C22, very short-duration rainfed lowland variety IR58, and promising upland variety IR9575 Sel. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Fertilizer treatments were the mainplots and rice entries the subplots.

The trial was conducted 19 Nov 1987-20 Mar 1988 at Bontobili experimental farm, under agroclimatic zone B₂ (7-9 mo with monthly rainfall more than 200

Performance of rice hybrids and conventional varieties under upland conditions, with and without fertilizer. Bontobili, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, 1987-88 wet season.

Entry	Plant height at harvest (cm)		Panicles (no./m ²)		Filled grains (no./panicle)		Grain yield (t/ha at 14% moisture)	
	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer
V41A/IR54	93.0	82.0	263	205	83	72	2.4	1.9
V41A/Sadang	98.7	81.7	263	223	87	76	1.8	1.7
V20B	73.1	72.3	367	196	74	72	2.1	1.6
Sadang	102.3	82.7	291	204	79	79	2.2	1.7
Tondano	122.7	106.7	259	177	84	75	2.7	2.0
IR58	73.7	67.0	373	185	78	51	2.2	1.8
C22	145.0	118.3	252	191	95	93	2.4	1.9
IR9575 Sel	129.3	101.7	253	179	124	113	3.4	2.2
Mean	104.8	89.1	280	195	88	79	2.39	1.86
CV (%)								
(a)		7		16		12		19
(b)		8		13		11		16
LSD (5%)								
(a)		7.9		48		ns		0.5
(b)		9.1		37		11		0.4

mm, and 2-3 mo with monthly rainfall less than 100 mm). Soil is Ultic Haplustalf, fine mixed, isohyperthermic. It has clay loam texture; pH 5.7;

available P (Bray₁) 39 ppm; 0.6, 8.8, 2.5, 0.2, and 0.3 meq exchangeable K, Ca, Mg, Na, and Al/ 100 g soils, respectively; and 0.1% total N and 1.8% organic

matter content.

Applying 135-40-50 kg NPK/ha as urea, TSP, and KCl respectively, significantly increased plant height of tall conventional varieties and hybrids.

Plant height of dwarf varieties V20B and IR58 was not significantly affected. The two rice hybrids were more susceptible to rice blast disease with 135 kg N/ha. The other entries were not

affected by blast. Yields of hybrids V41A/IR54 and V41A/Sadang were significantly lower than that of IR9575 Sel (see table). Therefore, these hybrids are not suited to upland conditions. □

Compatibility of six rice varieties with indica and japonica varieties

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Although the F₁ hybrids of indica/japonica crosses show semisterility, some rice varieties crossed with indica and japonica varieties produce fertile F₁ plants. These are known as wide compatible varieties (WCVs). We crossed CP-SLO₁₇, CP-SLO₁₉, 02428, Lunhui 422, Peiai 64, and SMR with six indica and six japonica testers.

The cultivars showed obvious differences in compatibility with indica and japonica varieties (see table). CP-SLO₁₇ and CP-SLO₁₉ were found to be WCVs. Cultivars 02428 and Lunhui 422 were more compatible with japonica than with indica varieties. Peiai 64 and SMR were more compatible with indicas, and were not designated WCVs. □

Fertility of F₁ spikelets in crosses of some rice cultivars and indica and japonica testers. HHRRC, Hunan, China, 1987.

Combination	F ₁ spikelet fertility (%)	
	Mean	Range
CP-SLO ₁₇ /indica	81.2	68.5-91.3
CP-SLO ₁₇ /japonica	85.4	78.4-92.0
CP-SLO ₁₉ /indica	80.0	73.3-86.5
CP-SLO ₁₉ /japonica	81.2	72.0-87.2
02428/indica	68.2	53.2-84.3
02428/japonica	84.2	78.4-92.4
Lunhui422/indica	74.2	68.5-89.4
Lunhui422/japonica	85.8	80.4-94.4
Peiai 64/indica	86.5	78.1-89.6
Peiai 64/japonica	60.3	41.2-85.3
SMR/indica	86.4	76.3-92.1
SMR/japonica	72.2	62.3-84.4
Indica/japonica	34.3	4.4-53.2

Salt tolerance of anther culture-derived rice lines

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Four dihaploid lines produced through the anther culture of IR51491 (IR4630-22-2-5-1-3/Pokkali) F₁ and IR51500 (IR5657-33-2/IR4630-22-2-5-1-3) F₁, and their parents were evaluated for salt tolerance, using water culture technique

in the phytotron glasshouse at 29/21 °C (day/night temperature) and 70% relative humidity. Cultivars Pokkali and Nona Bokra were the tolerant checks.

IR51491 was designed to incorporate the semidwarf trait of IR4630-22-2-5-1-3 (Pelita I-1/Pokkali/IR2061-464-2/IR1820-52-2) into salt-tolerant Pokkali. IR51500 was designed to incorporate high-yielding traits into IR4630-22-2-5-1-3. The semidwarf IR4630 has compact tillering, poor

1. Relative response of anther culture lines and parents of IR51491 (IR4630-22-2-5-1-3/Pokkali) and of IR51500 (IR5657-33-2/IR4630-22-2-5-1-3) at salinity of 12 dS/m. IRRI, 1988.